

Teachers' Perception on the Status ... (Aliu, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15258606>

Teachers' Perception of the Status of Teaching and Learning of Sciences among Secondary School Students in Zamfara State: Implications for Sustainable Development Goals

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Abstract

To achieve quality education as one of the goals of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), it requires effective teaching and learning at all educational levels in Nigeria. This study therefore adopted a descriptive survey research design to find out the perception of science teachers in both male and female secondary schools on teaching and learning sciences in Zamfara state, this is to ascertain that the system of education practice in the state comply with SDGs. Population of the study consists of all public Secondary School Science Teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in Zamfara State. A Sample size of 158 (Male=70 and Female=88) teachers were drawn from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. Four research questions were raised and one hypothesis was tested. The data were collected using a structured questionnaire (STQTLPSS) developed by the researchers in line with the indicators of SDGs goal 4 target 4a. The instrument was validated and reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained using Cronbach's Alpha reliability test. The data were analysis using descriptive statistics and Mann-Whitney U-Test. The result of the study revealed that teaching and learning of science subjects at senior secondary schools in Zamfara state has not reach expectation to meet up with target 4a of SDGs as the response of science teachers pointed out some challenges hindering their effectiveness in teaching. Also there are significant difference in some aspect of teaching and learning of science subjects between male schools and female schools. Among others, significant difference existed in the level of students' engagement in the lesson. This call for gender equality in the teaching of science subjects at secondary schools in Zamfara state. It was concluded that the situation of teaching and learning in Zamfara state as not be adequately on the track of SDGs. It was recommended that state government and school administrators should put in place all what it requires in making effective teaching and learning of science subjects at senior secondary schools and establishing mechanism to maintain gender equality.

Keywords: Teachers' perception, teaching and learning, attainment, SDG, science teachers

Introduction

Considering the environmental problems experienced today, living in a balance and harmony with nature can only be achieved through formal education. Education is a prerequisite for sustainable development, which reveals the idea of a more viable world and a better future. Education has a role in promoting country cultures. A way to facilitate the children to be a good citizen and promote Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is through science learning. Science is in line with children characteristics because, naturally, children were born to learn about science with their high curiosity. They will do an active process to know and to understand the world around them and they are able to acquire new knowledge of the activity (Syaodih & Mulyana, 2017). Through quality science education, children are able to know and realize their environmental conditions. Science education is fundamental to achieving several Sustainable Development Goals (SGDs), particularly Goal 4 (Quality Education) and Goal 13 (Climate Action).

Quality science education as noted by UNESCO (2020) equips learners with critical thinking skills necessary for addressing complex global challenges. In Nigeria, where issues such as poverty, health crises, and environmental degradation

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are prevalent, effective science teaching can empower students to contribute to sustainable solutions. Science will enhance children's pride of their country and its culture, for instance to make them realize that they live in a rich country and should be grateful for it. In addition, children will be aware of existing environmental issues by knowing the cause and looking for a solution to the problems (Karaarslan & Teksöz, 2016). Science education can be a driving force in efforts to reduce poverty, violence and injustice (Holbrook, 2009). Creative and innovative science learning can utilize natural resources to develop physical products or ideas that are marketable, such as strategies for teaching children to plant crops, caring for animals, which results can be used to fulfil children's nutrition. Learning science for early childhood can also be done collaboratively; invite children to learn and to work together in solving environmental problems with peers without differentiating gender, ethnicity, or social status. Science learning is also very concerned about security principles that avoid violent behavior (Mulyana, Lidinillah & Syaodih, 2019).

One of the discussions on SDGs in Goal 4 is regarding quality education which discusses "ensuring education that is inclusive and of equal quality, also supports lifelong learning opportunities for all. This is to imply that for sustainable development goals to occupy in a society both individuals and the Governments at all level should embrace accessibility to quality education. Therefore, education becomes the indices for measuring the development capacity of both the individuals and the country at large. It becomes an important social commodity that is desired by all but relatively not affordable by all either on account of scarce resources or ill equipped teaching. This perhaps explains why UNESCO and World Education Forum (2015) recognize the global momentum of achieving accessible and quality education for children and adults. The term quality education is the process through which an individual is transformed into a participant in the social and economic development of his society (Daura and Audu, 2015). Quality education entails some standard or degree of excellence of the education system in meeting up with its desired goals. According to Elujekwute (2019) quality education covers the curriculum content, the instructional strategies, assessment and evaluation policies and procedures which determine the achievement and performance of the learners.

The imperative of quality education was stressed in Federal Republic of Nigeria National Policy on Education (FRN, 2004) where it states that the success of any education lies on proper planning, efficient administration and adequate funding and it expects these management service in education to achieve specified goals which include; (a) Assurance of quality control through regular and continuous supervision of instructional and other educational services. (b) Provision of efficient administrative and management control for maintenance and improvement of the system. SDGs does not left out the inclusion of women in every other goals particularly Goal 4 mention in Goal 5 (gender equality). SDG Goal 5 bring forward issue of gender based such as 5(1): End discrimination against women and girls and 5(C): Adopt and strengthen policies and enforceable legislation for gender equality. Achieving SDG 5 is a priority that contributes to increase in global well-being (Filho et al., 2022). According to Sen (2019), SDG5' targets are more fulsome and robust addressing different aspects of gender equality in economic, political and social. This study focuses on teachers' views on teaching and learning science at senior secondary schools to ascertain the level of attainment of sustainable development goals (4 and 5) and their centrality in the provision of information and knowledge and how this, in turn, can be used in the attainment of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) at the national and local level.

Furthermore, the policy document of the SDGs was designed to be applicable in line with the different national realities, capacities, level of development and national aspirations. By implication, it could be said that effective implementation of the programme demands enhanced capacity of the populace and inclusiveness of the various sectors of the society (Anthony, 2022). Through effective teaching and learning, the learners are gradually equipped to face the demands of a more sustainable world. It is expected that the emerging educational goals, philosophy, strategies, improved curricula and pedagogical interventions on the education sector will contribute their quota immensely to the attainment of the SDGs. In effect, the teachers, especially the science teachers have a major role to play in the realization of these goals (Anthony, 2022). The major challenge of implementing any education programme lies squarely on the teachers. This is because the quality of teachers in any educational system will greatly affect the quality of teaching and learning that prevails in the system (FME, 2013). In other words, teachers at all levels are regarded as the Centre hub of any educational process. This therefore implies that the science teachers who are charged with the responsibility of executing educational programmes in the nation should not only be aware of both national and global demands but should equally be adequately equipped to understand the situation of teaching and learning towards these demands.

Teachers hold a special position towards advancing the attainment of these goals because they localize content knowledge that brings about positive behavioral change in people, especially the younger generation. Teachers are fundamental to the development of any nation because they are an effective catalyst in the process of lifelong learning, which is fundamental

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for the attainment of any goal, especially the global goals. They mediate between educational content and the learners (Nwangwa and Inatimi, 2019). It is in this regard that they are truly the yardstick that measures the achievements and aspirations of the nation. The worth and potentialities of a country get evaluated in the work of teachers. It was in this direction that Musa, Jimba and Ogundele (2015) argued that the people of a country are the enlarged replica of their teachers because the teachers are the real nation builders. The teacher is the key of successful education as well as the achievement of SDGs. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2009) confirms this by stating that "no nation can rise above the quality of its teachers". In this connection, it can be safely inferred that no meaningful transformation can be achieved in Nigeria without the teachers playing their roles. Therefore, the task of achieving any societal goal ably rests on teachers because they are responsible for effecting attitudinal change in the learners.

It has been argued that teachers serve as models for their students (Cheung 2020); hence, teachers' perspectives and how these are enacted, will influence their students. Vukic (2019) noted that if education is to help students change towards a lifestyle that is undergirded by sustainable development principles there is need for focus on those whose perspectives and actions will influence these students by the teachers. The task of teaching as carried out by teachers is shaped by their thoughts and actions. Researchers have long established that teachers' thinking and classroom practice are interrelated and as such, teachers' thinking influences their classroom instructional practice (Fischer and Hänze 2020). Teachers' views are often shaped by the beliefs they hold about curriculum, students, pedagogy and the learning process, which in turn influence learning outcomes. Therefore, sending clear and consistent signals to teachers about what to teach is an important component of teaching for sustainable development in schools. Delivering or facilitating sustainable development content without attention to how teachers understand, interpret, and internalize sustainable development principles will have little or no effect on classroom practice (Darling-Hammond et al. 2020). Specific to how teachers' views influence their teaching of sustainable development, Vukic (2019) noted that though teachers had general ideas about their responsibility towards sustainable development this did not translate to active practice in organizing and deliberately undertaking sustainability activities to influence students' behavior.

Teachers' perceptions are a major predictor of the use of new technologies in institutional settings as well as mode and level of implementation of any educational programme. Perception towards a programme will potentially influence its practice and success. Perception involves the identification and interpretation of information to understand an issue in the environment (Schacter, 2011). For the teachers' enhanced perception of the school curriculum, school environment, adequate funding, availability of resources and continuous training have a great role to play. A well informed and capable person is more likely to lend himself towards government policies and programmes than an uninformed one. Therefore, the government at all levels have a major role to play in ensuring that teachers are carried along in the planning and implementation of her programmes such as the SDGs and others. The level of awareness and the quality of knowledge possessed by the teachers on such programmes will have a marked effect on the way they are perceived. Invariably, this also will determine the level to which they are ready to deliver the teaching/learning process towards the realization of the goals of SGDs. Students are therefore able to relate what they learn in the classroom to their real life actions, and will increasingly be in a better position to take the lead in changing behaviours and adopting sustainable lifestyles in all their endeavours.

Statement of the Research Problem

Despite the importance of science education in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), there are concerns about the effectiveness of science teaching and learning in Nigerian senior secondary schools, particularly in Zamfara State. Studies have shown that teachers in Zamfara State often face challenges such as inadequate learning resources (Adeniran, 2020) and lack of professional development (Aminu & Samah, 2019). These factors can lead to an ineffective teaching of science than it could be. The system of education in practicing in Zamfara state that is co-educational (boys only and girls only) could be a gender bias in catering for effective teaching of science which may not support SDGs agenda at 2030. This global initiatives designed aiming to benefit daily lives of people cannot be implemented appropriately unless they are monitor and accountable. Teachers' views on teaching and learning science are crucial in understanding the challenges and opportunities in science education. There is hardly any information on science teachers at senior secondary schools views in monitoring of SDGs especially in the north-west Geo-political Zone of Nigeria. Furthermore, available studies on college of education lecturers' perception of SDGs (Anthony, 2022) failed to investigate the teachers' views on the teaching and learning sciences for the attainment of SDGs. Also, inadequacies of gender indicator will make it harder to accurately identify, analyze and monitor the separate needs in the two categories of the school system and develop effective evidence-based policies and solution (Odera & Mulusa, 2020). The need to fill these gaps and other similar ones necessitated this study.

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Objectives of the study

The following were the specific objective of the study:

1. To find out Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects at senior secondary schools in Zamfara state.
2. To find out Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male senior secondary schools in Zamfara state.
3. To find out Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state.
4. To determine the difference between the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male and female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects at senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?
2. What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?
3. What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?
4. What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male and female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?

Hypothesis

The following research hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significant:

H_{01} : There is no significant difference between perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male and female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state.

Methodology

The researchers adopted descriptive survey research design. The target population comprises 260 science teachers which include Physics, Chemistry, Biology and Mathematics teachers in co-educational public senior secondary schools in Zamfara state. Taro Yamen formula was used to arrive at sampling 158 science teachers. Purposive random sampling was used to select 20 schools (10 male schools and 10 female schools). Stratified random sampling was used to select 70 science teachers in male schools and 88 science teachers in female schools. The instrument title Science Teachers Questionnaire on Teaching and Learning Process of Science Subjects (STQTLPSS) was used for data collection. The STQTLPSS was developed by the researchers in line with the indicators of SDGs Goal 4 Target 4a. Section 1 of the instrument contains demographic data and section 2 contains 16 items in 4-point scale: strongly Agree (SA) – 4 points, Agree (A) – 3 points, Disagree (D) – 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) – 1. The instrument was validated and pilot tested. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined with Cronbach's Alpha and yielded 0.78. The instrument was administered and collected for collation from respondents. Research questions were answered using frequent count, mean and standard deviation and Mann-Whitney U-test was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significant. The benchmark for decision making was 2.50, any mean score greater than or equal to 2.5 indicated agreement while mean less than 2.5 indicated disagreement.

Results

Research Question 1:

What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects at senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of science teachers' response on the status of teaching and learning science subjects at senior secondary schools

Item	N	Responses				\bar{X}	S. Dev.	Remark
		SA	A	D	SD			
1	158	60	80	18	-	3.22	0.653	Agreed

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2	158	72	80	6	-	3.42	0.567	Agreed
3	156	34	58	44	20	2.68	0.957	Agreed
4	158	82	68	4	4	3.44	0.672	Agreed
5	156	32	90	28	6	2.95	0.734	Agreed
6	156	58	78	18	2	3.23	0.699	Agreed
7	150	46	70	30	4	3.05	0.784	Agreed
8	156	12	60	60	24	2.39	0.838	Disagreed
9	154	82	54	16	2	3.40	0.728	Agreed
10	154	18	34	52	50	2.13	1.001	Disagreed
11	156	52	82	12	10	3.13	0.809	Agreed
12	148	28	32	58	30	2.39	1.014	Disagreed
13	156	8	28	70	50	1.96	0.842	Disagreed
14	154	16	34	74	30	2.23	0.884	Disagreed
15	156	22	96	34	4	2.87	0.669	Agreed
16	156	46	58	42	10	2.90	0.903	Agreed
Grand Mean						2.84	0.797	Agreed

N: Number of respondents; \bar{X} = Mean; S. Dev. = Standard Deviation

Source: Field work, (2024)

Table 1 shows that science teachers agreed on items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11, 15 and 16 since their mean responses greater than 2.50. They disagreed on items 8,10,12,13 and 14 as their mean responses less than 2.50. This means that effective teaching and learning of science subjects at senior secondary schools in Zamfara state is not up to the task as the science teachers responded that they lack attending professional development; they have challenges of delivering effective teaching due to shortage of textbooks, lack of science practical equipments and too much work load; no enough qualified science teachers; lack of facilities to implement innovative teaching; and lack of the improvement on teachers' remuneration. The grand mean shows that science teachers agreed that there is improved situation of teaching and learning science subjects in senior secondary schools as mean = 2.84 and standard deviation = 0.797

Research Question 2:

What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?

Table 2: Descriptive analysis of male science teachers' response on the status of teaching and learning science subjects at male senior secondary schools

Item	N	Responses				\bar{X}	S. Dev.	Remark
		SA	A	D	SD			
1	70	24	30	16	-	3.11	0.753	Agreed
2	70	26	44	-	-	3.37	0.487	Agreed
3	68	12	26	16	14	2.53	1.014	Agreed
4	70	30	34	4	2	3.31	0.713	Agreed
5	70	10	48	8	4	2.91	0.697	Agreed
6	70	12	46	10	2	2.97	0.659	Agreed
7	68	14	28	22	4	2.77	0.849	Agreed
8	70	6	24	28	12	2.34	0.866	Disagreed
9	70	36	24	10	-	3.37	0.726	Agreed
10	70	10	12	26	22	2.14	1.026	Disagreed
11	70	16	38	6	10	2.86	0.937	Agreed
12	66	18	10	24	14	2.49	1.113	Disagreed
13	70	6	14	36	14	2.17	0.851	Disagreed
14	70	10	20	28	12	2.40	0.939	Disagreed
15	70	8	42	18	2	2.80	0.672	Agreed

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16	70	24	28	12	6	3.00	0.827	Agreed
Grand Mean						2.78	0.827	Agreed

N: Number of respondents; \bar{X} =Mean; S. Dev. = Standard Deviation

Source: Field work, (2024)

In table 2, it was also observed that male science teachers agreed on items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11, 15 and 16 since their mean responses greater than 2.50. They disagreed on items 8,10,12,13 and 14 as their mean responses less than 2.50. This means that effective teaching and learning of science subjects at male senior secondary schools in Zamfara state is not up to the task as the science teachers in the schools responded that they lack attending professional development; they have challenges of delivering effective teaching due to shortage of textbooks, lack of science practical equipments and too much work load; no enough qualified science teachers; lack of facilities to implement innovative teaching; and lack of the improvement on teachers' remuneration. The grand mean shows that science teachers agreed that there is improved situation of teaching and learning science subjects in senior secondary schools as mean = 2.78 and standard deviation = 0.827.

Research Question 3:

What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?

Table 3: Descriptive analysis of female science teachers' response on the status of teaching and learning science subjects at female senior secondary schools

Item	N	Responses				\bar{X}	S. Dev.	Remark
		SA	A	D	SD			
1	88	36	50	2	-	3.39	0.535	Agreed
2	88	46	36	6	-	3.46	0.624	Agreed
3	88	22	32	28	6	2.80	0.899	Agreed
4	88	52	34	-	2	3.55	0.624	Agreed
5	86	22	42	20	2	2.98	0.766	Agreed
6	86	46	32	8	-	3.44	0.662	Agreed
7	82	32	42	8	-	3.29	0.638	Agreed
8	86	6	36	32	12	2.42	0.818	Disagreed
9	84	46	30	6	2	3.43	0.733	Agreed
10	84	8	22	26	28	2.12	0.987	Disagreed
11	86	36	44	6	-	3.35	0.609	Agreed
12	82	10	22	34	16	2.32	0.928	Disagreed
13	86	2	14	34	36	1.79	0.799	Disagreed
14	84	6	14	46	18	2.10	0.816	Disagreed
15	86	14	54	16	2	2.93	0.665	Agreed
16	86	22	30	30	4	2.81	0.75	Agreed
Grand Mean						2.87	0.749	Agreed

N: Number respondents; \bar{X} =Mean; S. Dev. = Standard Deviation

Source: Field work, (2024)

As shown in table 3, female science teachers also agreed on items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11, 15 and 16 since their mean responses greater than 2.50. They disagreed on items 8,10,12,13 and 14 as their mean responses less than 2.50. This means that effective teaching and learning of science subjects at female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state is not up to the task as the teachers in schools responded that they lack attending professional development; they have challenges of delivering effective teaching due to shortage of textbooks, lack of science practical equipments and too much work load; no enough qualified science teachers; lack of facilities to implement innovative teaching; and lack of the improvement on teachers' remuneration. The grand mean shows that science teachers agreed that there is improved situation of teaching and learning science subjects in senior secondary schools as mean = 2.87 and standard deviation = 0.749

Research Question 4:

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What are the Perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male and female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state?

Table 4: Descriptive analysis comparing mean response of science teachers in male schools and those in female schools.

School Type	N	\bar{X}	S. Dev.	Mean Difference
Male School	70	2.78	0.827	0.09
Female School	88	2.87	0.749	

N: Number respondents; \bar{X} =Mean; S. Dev. = Standard Deviation

Source: Field work, (2024)

As revealed in the table 4, the mean response of science teachers in female senior secondary schools (2.87) is higher than the mean response of science teachers in male senior secondary schools (2.78) with mean difference of 0.09. This implies that science teachers in female secondary schools rate teaching and learning process of science subjects higher compare to what is obtainable in male secondary schools.

Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between perceptions of science teachers on the status of teaching and learning of science subjects among male and female senior secondary schools in Zamfara state.

Table 5: Mann-Whitney U-Test analysis comparing the mean responses of science teachers in male secondary schools and those in female secondary schools

Item	School Type	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	U-Test	Sig.	Remark
1	Male School	70	71.30	4991.00	2506.000	0.026	S
	Female School	88	86.02	7570.00			
2	Male School	70	74.73	5231.00	2746.000	0.184	NS
	Female School	88	83.30	7330.00			
3	Male School	68	72.53	4932.00	2586.000	0.129	NS
	Female School	88	83.11	7314.00			
4	Male School	70	72.53	4932.00	2516.000	0.025	S
	Female School	88	83.11	7314.00			
5	Male School	70	77.13	5399.00	2914.000	0.701	NS
	Female School	86	79.62	6847.00			
6	Male School	70	62.64	4385.00	1900.000	0.000	S
	Female School	86	91.41	7861.00			
7	Male School	68	61.32	4170.00	1824.000	0.000	S
	Female School	82	87.26	7155.00			
8	Male School	70	76.10	5327.00	2842.000	0.524	NS
	Female School	86	80.45	6919.00			
9	Male School	70	75.47	5283.00	2798.000	0.566	NS
	Female School	84	79.19	6652.00			
10	Male School	70	77.70	5111.00	2926.000	0.958	NS
	Female School	84	77.33	5915.00			
11	Male School	70	66.50	4655.00	2170.000	0.001	S
	Female School	86	88.27	7591.00			
12	Male School	66	77.44	5111.00	2512.000	0.434	NS
	Female School	82	72.13	5915.00			
13	Male School	70	89.04	6233.00	2272.000	0.005	S
	Female School	86	69.92	6013.00			
14	Male School	70	85.30	5971.00	2394.000	0.034	S
	Female School	84	71.00	5964.00			
15	Male School	70	74.13	5189.00	2704.000	0.209	NS

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16	Female School	86	82.06	7057.00	2608.000	0.132	NS
	Male School	70	84.24	5897.00			
Overall	Female School	86	73.83	6349.00	2514.000	0.246	NS
	Male School	70	77.54	5201.00			
Test	Female School	88	86.68	6912.00			

N: Number respondents; S: Significant; NS: Not Significant

Source: Field work, (2024)

Table 5 shows that the hypothesis was accepted in items 2, 3, 5, 8, 9, 10, 12, 15, and 16. This means that significant difference does not exist in the mean response of science teachers in male senior secondary schools and those in female secondary schools on the items since $P > 0.05$ in each of them. But, significant difference existed in the mean response on items 1, 4, 6, 7, 11, 13 and 14 showing that teaching and learning of sciences are difference as a result of differences in the teachers knowledge about relevance of curriculum, students engagement in the lesson, the rate of students assessment, methods of students assessment, level of administrative support, challenges of implementing innovative teaching techniques and the level of teachers commitment in teaching due to poor remuneration respectively. The mean response on 1, 4, 6, 7, and 11 are in favour of female schools while mean response on 13 and 14 are in favour of male schools. This means that there is need for balance in some aspects of teaching and learning in both male schools and female schools to avoid gender bias. The overall test shows that in the general response, there is no significant difference between the mean response of science teachers in male schools and those in female school ($U = 2514.000$, $P > 0.05$) but teaching and learning rank higher in female school than male school as their mean ranks are 5201 and 6812 for male schools and female schools respectively.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that teaching and learning of science subjects at both male and female secondary schools operating in Zamfara state still requires more effort from the state and agents such as science teachers and school administration to improve it status up to the task. In spite of general agreement of science teachers that there is improved teaching and learning of science subjects in their schools, the findings show that there are several challenges which hinder their effectiveness. The challenges are lack of the opportunity to attend professional development programme, shortage of textbooks, lack of science practical equipments, too much work load, no enough qualified science teachers, lack of facilities to implement innovative teaching and lack of the improvement on teachers' remuneration. This findings acknowledge the findings of Fomunyan (2019) which identified the challenges facing in Nigeria secondary schools which hindering effectiveness of teaching and learning of science at that level as lack of infrastructure and facility, lack of digitalization of Nigeria education, brain drain which resulted to lack of qualified science teachers, low salary and lack of incentives for science teachers. The findings also support the findings of Sodangi et al. (2022) which reported that secondary school science teachers in Zamfara state have not been participating professional development programmes.

The study also revealed that in Zamfara state, the effective condition of teaching and learning of science in female schools is now more than what is obtainable in male secondary schools. This could be that more focus as been put on female education as the evidence of the report of Stoet and Greary (2018) that almost all countries have concern on underrepresented of female in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) and the strength and pursuit increase as the increase in national gender equality. Furthermore, the findings reveal discrepancies in some aspects of teaching and learning of science between male secondary schools and female secondary schools. It was revealed that there were significant differences in some aspects which some favour female schools and some favour male schools. The aspects in which differences existed are teachers knowledge about relevance of curriculum, students engagement in the lesson, the rate of students assessment, methods of students assessment, level of administrative support, challenges of implementing innovative teaching techniques and the level of teachers commitment in teaching due to poor remuneration. These aspects are related to teaching strategies and pedagogy and these are the heart of teaching influence effective teaching and learning. The aspects missing by male schools counterbalanced those one missing by female schools that is why at the end there was no significant difference existed. As noted by Obidovna (2023) effective teaching strategies and pedagogies can serve as basis for updating and improving teaching practice in modern condition. Therefore, these aspects identified needs attention to be improved upon for effective teaching and learning.

Implication of findings on SDGs

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The 2030 agenda for sustainable development came into effect on 1st of January, 2016. The SDGs possess several useful targets which hopefully will make a better live for everyone. This agenda is gradually coming to an end period. Therefore, there is needs to understand how far the achievement of it. According to Odera and Mulusa (2020), one of the limitations in implementing Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) is lack of proper monitoring and report progress. The researchers intended to use the findings of this to determine if the teaching and learning of science at senior secondary schools in Zamfara state is on the track of SDGs due to the system of education practice in the state. The SDGs goal 4 is to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. This is to provide effective teaching and in the schools. Hence the findings shows that Zamfara state is yet to meet the target of this aspect of the agenda because there are some aspect of teaching and learning of science need to improve upon. Gender equality also is a goal (Goal 5) that cut across every other goal. Since it was observed from the findings that there are discrepancies in the missing aspect of teaching and learning of science in both male schools and female schools, the issue of gender equality need to be address in the teaching and learning at secondary schools.

Conclusion

It was concluded from the findings of this study that the situation of teaching and learning of science subjects among senior secondary schools need to be address in order to be in line with SDGs.

Recommendations

The researchers recommended that state government and school administrators should put in place all what it require in making effective teaching and learning of science subjects at senior secondary schools and establishing mechanism to maintain gender equality. Hence, the following are recommended:

1. The ministry of education and school administrators should regularly give science teachers the opportunity to attend professional development in their field.
2. School administrators should find means of providing adequate materials for effective teaching and learning.
3. School administrator should support by providing require facilities and amenities for implementing innovative teaching techniques.
4. The school should also set a quality assurance committee to frequently check what teachers are doing in class with students to maintain quality teaching.
5. State government should recruit more qualified science teachers and equally share to schools.
6. State government should improve remuneration of teachers and science teachers should be more committed in their profession for better future of students.

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